

**On the international benchmarking of permeability
predictions in anisotropic reference porous media:
*Insights from a multi-participant computational study***

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PARTICIPANTS AND SOFTWARE TOOLS OVERVIEW

Calculation of permeability benchmark

Entry ID	Organisation	Software, software version
B	Faserinstitut Bremen e.V. (FIBRE), University of Bremen, Germany	OpenFOAM,Version 9
C	IMT Nord Europe, Institute Mines-Telecom, Center for Materials and Processes, Lille, France	FEMS,4.3
D	Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering (INEGI), Porto, Portugal	ANSYS,2023 R2; OpenFOAM,v202406
E	Koc University, Istanbul, Türkiye	ANSYS,2024 R1
F	Khalifa University of Science and Technology, Abu Dhabi, UAE	OpenFOAM,v202406
G	KU Leuven, Department of Materials Engineering, Belgium	FlowTex,
H	Leibniz-Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, Kaiserslautern, Germany	GeoDict, (voxel 100),SP1 for Windows, Revision 82612; ESI OpenCFD Release v2312
J	University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK	ANSYS,2024 R1
K	INRAE, 147, rue de l'Université, Paris Cedex, France	Comsol
L	Quantiflex Simulations SAS, Nantes, France	PORESPY,2.4.2+2.8.2; OpenFOAM,Version 8
M	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany.	OpenFOAM,Version 6
N	Nantes Universite, Ecole Centrale Nantes, Nantes, France	

REFERENCE MEDIUM

Unit cell

Periodic assembly

OVERVIEW & OBJECTIVES

Overview

- Numerical benchmark study focused on **simulating in-plane (K11(Kxx), K33 (Kzz)) and through-thickness (K22 (Kyy)) permeability of an engineered textile-like reference medium**
- The computer-aided design (CAD) file represents a **3D-printable porous structure** intended for **calibration of permeability test rigs**
- Data collected from multiple simulation teams using **identical geometry**

Objectives

- Assess **variability** of permeability prediction by the participants from multiple institutions using the same digital geometry
- Establish **reference values (K11, K22, K33)** based on consensus reported by simulation results
- Support **future calibration** of experimental setups through a **well-characterized, repeatable digital reference medium**

POROSITY FRACT- UNIT CELL

Organisation who calculated K	Porosity (%)
B.1	34.1
B.2	34.1
C.1	34.1
C.2	34.1
D.1	34.1
D.2	34.1
E	34.1
F	34.1
G.1	34.4
G.2	34.1
H.1	34.1
H.2	34.1
H.3	34.1
H.4	34.1
H.6	34.1
J	34.0
K	34.0
L.1	34.0
L.2	34.0
M	34.1
N	34.1

POROSITY FRACTION- PERIODIC ASSEMBLY

Organisation who calculated K	Porosity (%)
B	34.1
C	34.1
D	34.1
E	34.1
F	
G	---
H	34.1
J	34.0
K	34.0
L	34.0
M	34.1
N	34.1

OVERVIEW OF KXX, KY Y, KZZ STATISTICS

Component	Typical range	Notes
Kxx	~5.76E-11 to ~1.8E-08	Most values are clustered between 2.4×10^{-9} and $3.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$, with a few outliers on the higher end (notably 1.80×10^{-8} and $9.49 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$).
Kyy	~4.63E-12 to ~2.424E-9	The most variable component of all three directions. This could reflect asymmetric flow pathways, differences in mesostructural alignment, or artifacts from simulation resolution.
Kzz	~1.49E-11 to ~8.79E-09	Relatively consistent compared to Kyy, with many values close to $6\text{--}7 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$ Outliers (e.g., 8.79×10^{-9} and 4.22×10^{-9}) suggest localized channels or voxel resolution effects.

PERMEABILITY COMPARISON: UNIT CELL VS PERIODIC ASSEMBLY

Comparison of Permeability Tensor Components

CORRELATION

- K_{xx} and K_{zz} may have moderate correlation.
- Off-diagonal terms are negligible; cross-correlation with diagonal terms is insignificant

SYMMETRY CONSISTENCY

Looking at whether $K_{12} = K_{21}$, $K_{13} = K_{31}$, etc.

Cross-term symmetry	Pattern
Y/Y/Y (Symmetric)	Reported by OpenFOAM (B) and FEMS (C) runs
N/N/N (Asymmetric)	Reported by GeoDict and many others: may reflect minor numerical asymmetries or anisotropy.

OBSERVATIONS

- Anisotropy is evident, with K_{xx} consistently larger than K_{yy} and K_{zz} in most samples.
- Outliers in K_{yy} and K_{zz} suggest localized flow instabilities or non-uniform compaction..
- Measurement robustness is acceptable for K_{xx} and K_{zz} ; however, K_{yy} data would benefit from increased replicates or better control of preform architecture.
- Off-diagonal terms (K_{12} , K_{13} , K_{23}) are generally very small or zero, indicating near-symmetry and negligible coupling effects.
- Symmetry indicators ($K_{12}=K_{21}$ etc.) mostly “Y” but some “N” or “N (diff X%)” showing small asymmetries.
- Porosity mostly consistent around 34%.

FUTURE WORK / NEXT STEPS

Investigate the effect of geometric scale on permeability predictions

- Perform CFD simulations on scaled versions of the current RVE geometry:
RVE × 0.1 and **RVE × 0.01**
- Analyze whether the **permeability tensor \mathbf{K}** remains clustered (directionally consistent and within the same order of magnitude) across scales
- Document any shifts in anisotropy or permeability magnitude due to scale changes

Motivation:

- Understanding scale dependence is crucial for **validating CFD results** when extrapolating from microscale geometries to macroscale behaviors
- Although physical 3D printing and experimental validation of very small-scale RVEs may not be feasible, simulation outcomes can still inform:
 - Limitations of current CAD-based permeability predictions
 - Guidelines for scale selection in future digital calibration designs

Broader impact:

- Enhances the **robustness of digital twin strategies** for permeability benchmarking
- Supports development of **scalable reference materials** for various rig sizes and flow regimes

PHASE II: ENLARGED RVE ANALYSIS

- New geometry scaled $\times 2.8$ used for experimental validation
- Participants to simulate and report **Kxx**, **Kyy**, **Kzz**

(a) Unit cell CAD design with all channels, (b) CAD model of the full-scale interconnecting channel (All dimensions are in mm).

KEY REFERENCES FOR PERMEABILITY BENCHMARK

1. May et al., 2024

A new ISO standard for the experimental characterization of in-plane permeability of fibrous reinforcements

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2. Annamalai et al., 2025

On the extension of in-plane permeability calibration to out-of-plane measurements: Advancements in additively manufactured textile-structured porous media for liquid composite moulding

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3. Machado et al., 2023

On the understanding of bubble dynamics through a calibrated textile-like porous medium using a machine learning based algorithm

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4. Bodaghi et al., 2021

Surface quality of printed porous materials for permeability rig calibration, Journal of Composite Materials, Pages 548-558,

doi.org/10.1080/10426914.2021.1960994

5. Bodaghi et al., 2020

Additively manufactured three dimensional reference porous media for the calibration of permeability measurement set-ups

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